

Levels of satisfaction at Bahay Tsinoy as perceived by Filipino and foreign tourists

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Abstract

A satisfaction evaluation is an excellent predictor of tourist behavior in a destination. Thus, this study was conducted at Bahay Tsinoy, located in the Walled City, also known as Intramuros. This research focuses on tourist satisfaction and is influenced by two variables, Filipino and foreign tourists. The possible factors were collected in a survey questionnaire to scrutinize their perceptions and experiences when they visited Bahay Tsinoy. The selection of respondents is random but classified by their age, gender, and nationality. The use of descriptive research was applied in this study. Findings revealed that the tourists were satisfied with six characteristics of Bahay Tsinoy: Historical and Cultural Significance, Physical Appearance, Accessibility, Safety, Service, and Price. However, three of these six characteristics need immediate attention; Accessibility, Service, and Physical Appearance. This study also aims to give importance to understanding the tourists' side and perspective. The output of this study is the formulation of a promotional plan to boost tourism in the museum by enhancing and developing the six variables in the study. Implementing the promotional plan can help the museum educate the tourists more as well as make it more accessible, give it a better service, and offer a good price that is worth the visit.

Keywords: Accessibility; Bahay Tsinoy; Culture significance; Intramuros; Tourist satisfaction.

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Introduction

The tourism industry is crucial for the economy of both developing and developed countries. Tourism has developed over the past few decades (Vanhove, 2001); similar to what Cronin and Brady (2000) have mentioned, customer satisfaction has been a huge topic in research about this field because it can affect how customers act and how likely they are to stay with a business. Consumer satisfaction has been described in many different ways, including cognitive or affective views, as well as approaches that look at specific or overall experiences from a transaction (Høst & Knie-Anderson, 2004).

Bahay Tsinoy was constructed in the year 1999 by the Kaisa Para Sa Kaunlaran Inc. It was built to advocate the history and culture of Chinese-Filipino history (Aurelio et al., 2022). The museum showcases the past culture wherein the Chinese influenced Filipinos from earlier days until the present. Bahay Tsinoy became a well-known museum for students to learn Chinese-Filipino history throughout the years. The museum displays items from the pre-Spanish Chinese Era. The museum also satisfies tourists with items that showcase the history of Filipino-Chinese history (Leang et al., 2001).

Bahay Tsinoy is a museum that documents the history, lives, and contributions of the ethnic Chinese in Philippine life and history. It is owned by Kaisa Heritage Center, a non-profit organization co-founded by Teresita Ang-See, and it is located at 32 Anda corner Cabildo St. Intramuros, Manila. The highlight of the museum is the Acapulco Galleon trade. During the Spanish period, the Acapulco Galleon trade brought many valuable goods such as spices and porcelain in exchange for new world silver using the route they had established, traveling from China to Manila and then to Spain. Also, the museum showcases the rise of Chinese Filipinos into the uppermost of business and government. The museum tells the story of the contributions of Chinese-Filipino people during Spanish colonialism and World War II, such as joining the guerilla under the Japanese occupation, forming a unit to aid their fellow Filipino friends, and fighting the Japanese army. During the time of the Spaniards, they have called them as sangleys as to have the Spaniards mistreated them for having a mass growth of population in the Philippines. In the museum, you can see different kinds of wax figures that wore different kinds of clothing; it shows us to what are the different kinds of jobs in the society in the past that Tsinoy brought to the Philippines, which were merchants, traders, vendors, barbers, and a public reader. They also have shown in the museum a two-story house made from stone, called “Bahay na Bato.” It also interprets the past, stating that owning a two-story house indicates a high standard of life, and most residences contain a sari-sari store on the first level. Bahay Tsinoy’s strong point, as it has many competitors in the area, is to highlight the history and contributions of Chinese people who resided in the Philippines.

This research aims to determine the level of satisfaction of local and foreign tourists in terms of accessibility, cultural significance, physical appearance, safety, service, and price that will help Bahay Tsinoy to be known as one of the best tourist destinations in Intramuros that provides unique arts and historical events of Chinese-Filipino. By identifying and measuring tourist satisfaction, the researchers aim to gather the experience of the tourists, both negative and positive reactions toward the characteristics of Bahay Tsinoy.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to determine the level of satisfaction of Filipino and foreign tourists toward Bahay Tsinoy. Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Gender
 - 1.2. Age
 - 1.3. Classification of Tourists
2. What is the level of satisfaction of Filipino and Foreign tourist in Bahay Tsinoy in terms of:
 - 2.1. Accessibility
 - 2.2. Cultural Significance
 - 2.3. Physical Appearance
 - 2.4. Safety
 - 2.5. Services
 - 2.6. Price

Theoretical Framework

According to Cannon’s Cannon-Bard Theory of Emotion (1920), the brain contains an area responsible for reacting to emotional experiences. Satisfaction is a pleasant emotion that happens when an expectation is fulfilled or surpassed, whereas dissatisfaction is an unpleasant emotion that occurs as part of the anger reaction. Tourists who visited Bahay Tsinoy had their own standards or perspectives that satisfied

or dissatisfied their emotions. The researchers utilized this framework as a reference to determine whether tourists are content or unsatisfied with the characteristics of Bahay Tsinoy.

Figure 1. Cannon Bard-Theory is used in the level of satisfaction of Filipino and foreign tourists in Bahay Tsinoy.

Related Literature

According to Towner and Wall (1991), realizing the past can help in better understanding tourism. Huh (2002) also said that the tourists' characteristics are also significant factors in their satisfaction. According to his study, a well-known image of the relationship between cultural/heritage location qualities and tourists' overall happiness was investigated using demographic and tour behavior characteristics. Furthermore, a future study can examine the connection between tourists' satisfaction and their willingness to return to a location. A destination might be a factor in the repeated visits of tourism marketers and researchers.

The social exchange theory was validated in Moyle et al.'s (2013) research to ascertain tourists' perceptions of tourism's influence. They concluded that tourists were aware of both the good and negative effects of tourism growth. According to Gaki et al. (2016), satisfaction is often influenced by movements and factors relevant to visitors' non-public interests, such as leisure activities. Aside from that, loyalty is influenced by the acts and features of tourist locations, such as tours, sightseeing, and folklore aspects.

Based on Adinegara et al. (2017), the factors that are frequently used to fulfill tourist satisfaction are the quality of service and the given price. In addition, Salleh (2013) states that a range of factors is identified to contribute to the enjoyment of a vacationer's journey. These include popular tourist attractions, breathtaking sceneries, delectable meals, caring, and dedicated employees, and kind locals. When tourists feel fulfilled and satisfied with their travels, they remind themselves of the wonderful experience through fancied local souvenirs. What tourists feel while or after participating in a tour activity also gives them great satisfaction. According to Lee (2015), visitor satisfaction with the manufacturing unit tour experience consists of seven components. These components are accommodation and dining facilities, inside accessibility, nearby attractions, external accessibility, provision of security and emergency systems, on-site attractions, and provision of information services. Regardless, satisfaction with the provision of security and emergency systems is the most significant and effective factor in overall satisfaction.

Based on Al-Ababneh's (2013) findings, service quality directly influences visitor satisfaction with the destination's amenities, accessibility, and attraction. As a result, the study concluded that service quality has a significant influence on tourist satisfaction and plays an important role in tourism in extending the degree of tourist contentment. In terms of accessibility, Mihaela (2014) stated that methods of tourist destination-making and general tourist satisfaction might be influenced by identity factors. These are the main factors to consider while choosing a trip and for personal knowledge: natural surroundings, accommodation, infrastructure, and tourism facilities. Furthermore, investing in the developments of these areas is regarded as one of the primary methods of enhancing destination competitiveness. In reality, their responsibility is frequently inter-cultural than managerial. In terms of services, Della Corte et al. (2015) explored the key aspects of consumer satisfaction that impact tourist services, focusing on the travel

industry. This stems from the irrefutable fact those tourists' good perceptions of the destinations' services, products, and other resources may lead to customer retention and positive word-of-mouth. A great tourist travel experience helps to increase destination loyalty. The degree of a tourist's devotion to a location is shown in their plans to return, along with their willingness to recommend the destination to others. Wang et al. (2019) mentioned that safety and security are significant concerns for most people who travel to other countries, and these issues have been a main focus in research for the last few decades. They also say that safety and security can affect the choices people make when planning their trips.

Synthesis

The researchers found similar studies to understand what concept could satisfy the interest of the tourist. According to Wang's (2016) research, the conceptual character of consumer satisfaction, as well as the numerous, sensitive, and vivid nature of the destination's image, creates the subject and variation in its measurement for tourist destinations. A range of approaches to evaluate satisfaction are available to destination managers and company owners. As a result, the researchers employed visitor satisfaction to gauge tourist interest in Bahay Tsinoy.

The researchers discovered comparable studies to define what aspects or features must be found during a museum visit to have a hold on visitor satisfaction within the museum. According to Anderson et al. (1994), their investigations revealed that various methods for consumer satisfaction are influenced by three antecedents: quality, price, and expectation. However, Adinegara et al. (2017), some of the most used factors that hinder providing tourist contentment are the quality of labor and the given price. Cheng-Fei Lee (2015) describes visitor satisfaction with the manufacturing unit tour experience as having seven components. Accommodation and dining facilities, interior accessibility, adjacent attractions, outdoor accessibility, supply of security and emergency systems, on-site attractions, and provision of information services are among these components. Regardless, the most important and effective component of overall satisfaction is satisfaction with the provision of security and emergency systems. Based on Al-Ababneh's (2013) findings, service quality directly influences visitor satisfaction with the destination's amenities, accessibility, and attraction. As a result, based on the researchers' observations, the researchers utilized Accessibility, Historical/Cultural Significance, Physical Appearance, Safety, Service, and Price to identify the Characteristics/Attributes of Bahay Tsinoy.

The researchers discovered a study on what Chinese influences were propagated in the Philippines to demonstrate their relationship throughout the country's history. Meanwhile, Akpedonu and Saloma (2017), the impact of Chinese culture in the Philippines was felt throughout the country's islands. As a result, the Philippines acquired not just Chinese commodities and things but also Chinese fashion and cuisine trends, art forms, and loanwords. Wang et al. (2017) have a direct influence on tourist satisfaction. This study discovered that the effects of the destination's quality on WOM are exclusive between genders while analyzing the effect of moderating variables such as gender and visit frequency. This study showed that word-of-mouth had a considerable influence on tourist destination choices. According to Mihaela (2014), identity characteristics may impact tourist destination-making procedures and overall visitor satisfaction. Natural surroundings, lodging, infrastructure, and tourism amenities are the major aspects to consider while planning a trip and for personal knowledge.

Furthermore, investing in these regions' growth is seen as one of the key means of increasing destination competitiveness. Della Corte et al. (2015) investigated the important elements of customer satisfaction influencing tourist services, focusing on the tourism industry. This is due to the undeniable fact that visitors' favorable views of the destinations' services, goods, and other resources may result in customer retention and positive word-of-mouth. A positive tourist travel experience contributes to increased destination loyalty. The degree of a tourist's attachment to an area is demonstrated by their plans to return, as well as their desire to promote the location to others.

Methodology

Research Design

This research used a descriptive research design in assessing and obtaining information to focus more on the perception of Bahay Tsinoy and the levels of satisfaction of both foreign and Filipino tourists. This design was utilized by researchers to collect data and obtain the necessary information for this study.

Sample

The original respondents of this research are 50 participants: 25 Filipino tourists and 25 foreign tourists, respectively. Due to the pandemic, the cases of COVID-19 are increasing day by day at that time; so they decided to reduce the number of participants to 30. The researchers picked a total of 30 participants in the research setting, consisting of 15 Filipino tourists and 15 foreign tourists.

The researchers used stratified random sampling to divide and identify the group of participants in the said study. Stratified random sampling is the method to identify the participants because, according to Davis (2015), stratified random sampling is a method from a population whereby the population is divided into subgroups, and units are randomly selected from the subgroups. For this study, the subgroups are Filipino and foreign tourists.

Instruments

Our research questionnaire has been validated and approved by two faculty members of St. Dominic College of Asia; to get the needed data, the researchers used a close-ended survey questionnaire as their research instrument. The questionnaire was divided into two parts. The first part of the questionnaire is the demographic profile that includes age, gender, and classification of tourists, while the second part of the questionnaire focuses on the (6) six features of Bahay Tsinoy that are being evaluated. These are accessibility, historical/cultural significance, physical appearance, safety, service, and price. The researchers used the Likert scale as their method to identify the tourists' satisfaction. The Likert scale is a five-point scale wherein it is used to express the participant's satisfaction on how satisfied or dissatisfied they are with a particular statement. The Likert Scale was composed of five points: 1 – Very Dissatisfied, 2 Dissatisfied, 3 – Neutral, 4 – Satisfied, and 5 – Very Satisfied. The five-point Likert Scale was interpreted in Table 1:

Table 1. 5-point Likert Scale

Scale	Verbal Interpretation	Range
1	Very Dissatisfied	1.00-1.80
2	Dissatisfied	1.81-2.60
3	Neutral	2.61-3.40
4	Satisfied	3.41-4.20
5	Very Satisfied	4.21-5.00

Data Collection

Researchers visited the museum last January 10, 2020, and February 7, 2020. The tourists answered their respective surveys with our printed-out questionnaires. Foreign tourists visiting Bahay Tsinoy are starting to decrease because of the pandemic. Participants answered the questions administered through closed-ended survey questionnaires. After they had answered the survey questions, researchers described and analyzed the responses given. For the survey to be both reliable and valid, it is important that the number of respondents is equal. Researchers also used the observation method and visited the museum

in collecting data. The ideal data gathering method is a closed-ended survey questionnaire, which is used to summarize the participants' responses in the study. It is also the most efficient technique to get a large amount of data from many people.

The following statistical tools and techniques were used to gather the data:

Frequency – Average. To calculate the data of the profile of the respondents, the frequency – and the percentage was used. The profile of the respondents is composed of the age, gender, and nationality that visited Bahay Tsinoy.

Weighted Arithmetic Mean. This part shows the statistical tool used to evaluate the survey outcome. It starts from the weighted arithmetic mean (average) to identify the percentage of the levels of satisfaction for foreign and Filipino tourists who visited Bahay Tsinoy.

Results and Discussion

Table 2. Respondent's Profile According to Gender (N = 30)

Gender	Male	Percentage	Female	Percentage
Foreign Respondents	8	53.33%	7	46.67%
Filipino Respondents	5	33.33%	10	66.67%
Total	13	43.33%	17	56.67%

As shown in Table 2, the percentage of foreign tourists among the male respondents is 53.33%, and among the female respondents are 46.67%. While, the percentage of Filipino tourists, the male respondent is 33.33%, and the female respondent has 66.67%. The result means that the most visitors, according to their gender, are females with an average of 56.67%.

Table 3. Respondent's Profile According to Age

Age Group	18 and below	19-24	25-30	31-above	Total
Foreign respondent	2	5	6	2	14
Percentage (%)	10%	30%	40%	20%	100%
Filipino respondent	2	5	6	2	15
Percentage (%)	10%	30%	40%	20%	100%

According to Table 3, both foreign and Filipino respondents are the same percentage; there are 10% who are 18 and below, 30% are 19-24, 40% are 25-30, and 20% are 31-above.

Table 4. Respondent's Profile According to their Classification

Classification of Tourist	No. of Tourists	Percentage
Filipino	15	50%
Foreign	15	50%
Total	30	100%

According to Table 4, the number of Filipino tourists is 15. While the number of foreign tourists among the respondents is also 15. The results show that the numbers of Filipino and foreign tourists among the respondents are equal.

Table 5. Level of Satisfaction of Tourists in terms of Accessibility

Accessibility	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Searchable in Navigational apps (Waze and Google Maps)	4.27	Very Satisfied
Public transportation availability	4.27	Very Satisfied
Accessibility of private transportation, including parking spaces	4.13	Satisfied
Total	4.22	Very Satisfied

Table 5 presents the level of satisfaction of tourists towards the accessibility of Bahay Tsinoy. Searchable in navigational apps (Waze and Google Maps) got an average score of 4.27. It is followed by public transportation availability got the same average score of 4.27. The lowest average score, 4.13, is the accessibility of private transportation, including parking spaces. The total average score is 4.22, which means that the tourists are very satisfied with how accessible Bahay Tsinoy is.

Table 6. Level of Satisfaction of Tourists in terms of Historical/Cultural Significance

Historical/Cultural Significance	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Artifacts portray the Chinese-Filipino culture in the Philippines	4.07	Satisfied
Availability of information about each exhibit display	4.07	Satisfied
Quality of wax figures	3.93	Satisfied
Total	4.02	Satisfied

Table 6 presents the level of satisfaction of the tourist toward the historical/cultural significance of the Bahay Tsinoy. The highest score given by the tourist is 4.07; two statements got the same average score. It implies that tourists are satisfied with the artifacts that portrayed the Chinese-Filipino culture in the Philippines,” then followed by the information of each exhibit display. With the lowest average score of 3.93 on the quality of wax figures implies that the tourist is satisfied with how Bahay Tsinoy portrays their historical/cultural significance. The total average score is 4.02, and it implies tourists are very satisfied with the historical/cultural significance of Bahay Tsinoy.

Table 7. Level of Satisfaction of Tourists in terms of Physical Appearance

Physical Appearance	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Ambiance of the museum	4.20	Satisfied
Outside appearance of the museum	4.07	Satisfied
The legitimacy of the displayed historical items	4.20	Satisfied
Total	4.15	Satisfied

Table 7 presents the level of satisfaction of tourists regarding the physical appearance of Bahay Tsinoy, the highest score of 4.20 shows on the table that the two statements got the same score, which means that tourist is satisfied with the “ambiance of the museum” and the “legitimacy of the displayed historical items.” The lowest average score got 4.07, which implies that tourists are satisfied with the outside appearance of the museum. With a total average score of 4.15, tourists are satisfied with the physical appearance of Bahay Tsinoy.

Table 8. Level of Satisfaction of Tourists in terms of Safety

Safety	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Safety signs and precautions, including security cameras	4.47	Very Satisfied
Availability of security personnel (guards)	4.53	Very Satisfied
Availability of first aid kits and qualified personnel to assist tourists in any emergency	3.87	Satisfied
Total	4.28	Very Satisfied

Table 8 presents the level of satisfaction of the tourists towards their experience of their safety in Bahay Tsinoy. The highest average score got 4.53 on the “availability of security personnel or guards.” It is followed by “safety signs and precautions including security cameras,” with an average score of 4.47. The lowest average score was 3.87, which means that tourists are satisfied with the first aid kits and qualified personnel if any emergency happens. The total average score is 4.28, and it implies that the tourists are very satisfied with their safety in the museum.

Table 9. Level of Satisfaction of Tourists in terms of Service

Service	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Quality of service with the use of technology	4.33	Very Satisfied
Facility availability such as comfort room	4.07	Satisfied
Level of services provided by the museum staff	4.07	Satisfied
Total	4.15	Satisfied

Table 9 presents the level of satisfaction of tourists with the services that Bahay Tsinoy offers to them, with an average of 4.33 is the highest score, and it implies the tourist is satisfied with the quality of service with the use of technology. It is followed by “facility availability such as comfort rooms” and “levels of services provided by the museum staff,” which got the same average score of 4.07. With the total average score of services being 4.15, it implies that the tourists who visit Bahay Tsinoy are satisfied with the services that they experience in the museum.

Table 10. Level of Satisfaction of Tourists in terms of Price

Price	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Affordability of the entrance fee	4.13	Satisfied
Discounts for students	4.27	Very Satisfied
Overall tour is worth the price	4.07	Satisfied
Total	4.15	Satisfied

Table 10 presents the level of satisfaction of the tourists regarding the prices that Bahay Tsinoy offers, with an average of 4.27 and the highest score is the discount for the students. It is followed by the affordability of the entrance fee with an average score of 4.13. The lowest average score was 4.07 by the “overall tour is worth the price.” With the total average score of the price being 4.15, it implies that the tourists who visited Bahay Tsinoy are very satisfied with the prices of the museum.

Hoogland (2016) pointed out that museums show the values, identities, and everyday experiences of the society around them. Feminist critique helps us look again at how we decide what counts as art, challenge the usual ideas about the cultural worth of things and their natural value, and think about how museums fit into a more inclusive and diverse cultural world.

Conclusions

The respondents included fifteen (15) Filipino and fifteen (15) foreign tourists who visited Bahay Tsinoy. Most of the foreign tourists are male. For the locals, most are female. Both foreign and Filipino respondents with the age 25-30 have frequently visited the museum. For accessibility, foreign tourists are satisfied with the accessibility of museums, and Filipino tourists are very satisfied. For historical and cultural significance, the foreign tourists are very satisfied with the provided information on historical significance, while Filipino tourists are on average of satisfaction. For the physical appearance, both foreign and Filipino tourists have average satisfaction when it comes to the physical appearance of the museum. For safety, foreign and Filipino tourists are very satisfied with the provided safety measures. For the service, there is an average satisfaction among foreign and Filipino respondents in terms of service provided. Lastly, for the price, foreign tourists are very satisfied while Filipino tourists are very satisfied with the affordability of the price.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations made by researchers:

1. Improve the accessibility of the transportation near the museum, such as parking and transportation.
2. Provide more artifacts related to Chinese-Filipino culture and improve the wax figures that make it more realistic in reminiscing the history that explains it.
3. The ambiance of the museum can be more pleasing if there are some developments in the exterior design of the building that may relate to the theme of the museum that portrays and improvement of some displayed historical items that need to be designed up to date and minor cleaning.
4. Provide first aid kits and emergency plans in the museum for safety purposes as well as fire exit planning.
5. Improve the quality of using some technology like digital learning in the museum such as tablets, smart television, and digital presentation and ensure the availability of the staff to guide the tourists in the museum.
6. Improve some discounts for students, persons with disabilities (PWD), and also apply for some vouchers and promo tours in the museum.

References

- Adinegara, G. N. J., Suprapti, N. W. S., Yasa, N. N. K., & Sukaatmadja, I. P. G. (2017). Factors that influences tourist's satisfaction and its consequences. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 9(8), 39-50. <https://www.iiste.org/Journals/index.php/EJBM/article/view/35898>
- Akpedonu, E., & Saloma, C. (2017). Manila's" Chinatown": Globalization and built heritage. *Social Transformations Journal of the Global South*, 5(2), 2. <https://doi.org/10.13185/2799-015X.1126>
- Al-Ababneh, M. (2013). Service quality and its impact on tourist satisfaction. *Institute of Interdisciplinary Business Research*, 4(12), 164-177.
- Anderson, E. W., Fornell, C., & Lehmann, D. R. (1994). Customer satisfaction, market share, and profitability: Findings from Sweden. *Journal of Marketing*, 58(3), 53-66. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002224299405800304>
- Aurelio, D. B., Diamante, V. E., & Gamboa, M. N. (2022). Heritage sites in the City of Manila as tourist attraction. *EARIST Research Journal*, 22(31), 60-71.
- Cronin Jr, J. J., Brady, M. K., & Hult, G. T. M. (2000). Assessing the effects of quality, value, and customer satisfaction on consumer behavioral intentions in service environments. *Journal of Retailing*, 76(2), 193-218. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4359\(00\)00028-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4359(00)00028-2)
- Davis, J. M. (2015). Sampling and what it means. In J. D. Brown & C. Coombe (Eds.), *The Cambridge guide to research in language teaching and learning* (pp. 198-205). Cambridge University Press.
- Della Corte, V., Sciarrelli, M., Cascella, C., & Del Gaudio, G. (2015). Customer satisfaction in tourist destination: The case of tourism offer in the city of Naples. *Journal of Investment and Management*, 4(1-1), 39-50. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.jim.s.2015040101.16>
- Gaki, E., Kostopoulou, S., Parisi, E., & Lagos, D. (2016). *The evaluation of tourism satisfaction in island destinations: The case of the Ionian Islands of Greece* [Conference paper]. 56th Congress of the European Regional Science Association: "Cities & Regions: Smart, Sustainable, Inclusive?", 23-26 August 2016, Vienna, Austria. https://www.econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/174645/1/Paper0295_EleniGaki.pdf
- Hoogland, M. A. S. (2016). *Toegankelijkheid in hedendaagse en moderne kunstmusea: Terug naar de tekentafel* (Master's thesis, Utrecht University). <https://studenttheses.uu.nl/handle/20.500.12932/24148>

- Høst, V., & Knie-Andersen, M. (2004). Modeling customer satisfaction in mortgage credit companies. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 22(1), 26-42. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02652320410514915>
- Huh, J. (2002). *Tourist satisfaction with cultural/heritage sites: The Virginia Historic Triangle* (Doctoral dissertation, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University). <https://vtechworks.lib.vt.edu/items/74e628c9-e063-4f5e-a80b-2a58388687e5>
- Leang, A. Y., Chua, S. C., & Capuno, V. P. (2001). *Bahay Tsinoy: A museum of the Chinese in Philippine Life (A proposed advocacy campaign for the Chinese-Filipino Integration into Philippine life)* [Bachelor's thesis, De La Salle University, Manila]. https://animorepository.dlsu.edu.ph/etd_bachelors/17661/
- Lee, C. F. (2015). Tourist satisfaction with factory tour experience. *International Journal of Culture, Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 9(3), 261-277. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCTHR-02-2015-0005>
- Mihaela, P. R. (2014). Customer satisfaction in tourism. How to measure it. *Cactus Tourism Journal*, 10(2), 30-35. https://www.cactus-journal-of-tourism.ase.ro/Pdf/vol10/paun_mihaela.pdf
- Moyle, B. D., Weiler, B., & Croy, G. (2013). Visitors' perceptions of tourism impacts: Bruny and Magnetic Islands, Australia. *Journal of Travel Research*, 52(3), 392-406. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047287512467702>
- Salleh, M., Omar, K., Yaakop, A. Y., & Mahmmod, A. R. (2013). Tourist satisfaction in Malaysia. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 4(5), 221-226.
- Towner, J., & Wall, G. (1991). History and tourism. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 18(1), 71-84. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0160-7383\(91\)90040-I](https://doi.org/10.1016/0160-7383(91)90040-I)
- Wang, T. L., Tran, P. T. K., & Tran, V. T. (2017). Destination perceived quality, tourist satisfaction and word-of-mouth. *Tourism Review*, 72(4), 392-410. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TR-06-2017-0103>
- Wang, Y. (2016). *More important than ever: Measuring tourist satisfaction*. Griffith Institute for Tourism, Griffith University. https://www.griffith.edu.au/__data/assets/pdf_file/0029/18884/Measuring-Tourist-Satisfaction.pdf
- Vanhove, N. (2001). Globalisation of tourism demand, global distribution systems and marketing. In S. Wahab & C. Cooper (Ed.), *Tourism in the age of globalisation* (pp. 137-170). Routledge. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9780203995853-13/globalisation-tourism-demand-global-distribution-systems-marketing-norbert-vanhove>